

THE MAIN REASONS FOR THE INCREASE IN THE TIME OF
MOVEMENT OF CARS OF THE CIS COUNTRIES ON THE TERRITORY
OF JSC "UZBEKISTAN RAILWAYS"

Egamberdiev Rustamjon Alievich

Tashkent state transport university, Uzbekistan

e-mail: rustam_ts1@mail.ru

Annotation. The fine is calculated at the rate of 1 times for the vacancy of rented and private (private) wagons belonging to the railway administration and other states. The average stopping of wagons on station tracks is determined by the ratio of the sum of stopping hours of all cars leaving the station track during the reporting period to the number of cars left.

Key words. Wagons, railway, direct, mixed, international, small, container, refrigerated container, consignor's route.

Introduction. Delivery of goods to the destination station on time is important for the economy of the state and is one of the main obligations of the railway under the contract of carriage. Therefore, Article 63 of the Charter stipulates that the railway must deliver the goods to the station of destination within the specified period. The calculation of the delivery time starts from 24 hours of the day of acceptance of the goods for carriage. Delivery time for goods accepted for carriage before the date of increase is 24 hours from the day of loading.

Methods. Delivery time: type of shipment (wagon, small, container, refrigerated container, consignor's route, etc.); transport speeds (cargo, large and passenger); depends on the type of flight (direct, mixed, international). Delivery time is determined by the following formula[1]:

$$T_{e.m.} = t_{ж.к.} + L_{ЮК} / v_{cyT} + \sum t_{к.о.}$$

where $t_{ж.к.}$ - time assigned to operations related to the shipment and receipt of goods;

$L_{\text{ЮК}}$ - the distance between the sending and receiving stations, km;

$v_{\text{цт}}$ - the speed of the load specified in the Rules of Carriage, km / day;

$t_{\text{к.о}}$ - is the time assigned to additional operations.

The times assigned to operations related to the dispatch and acceptance of goods, the assigned speeds of cargo and the times assigned to additional operations shall be taken from the Rules of Carriage of Goods.

The time of delivery of goods, as well as empty wagons owned or leased by the organization and individuals, is calculated at the station of departure, based on the distance charged, taking into account the railway routes through which the cargo is transported. Calculation of the time of delivery of goods, in accordance with the Rules for calculating the time of delivery of goods by rail, begins at 0.00 the next day of the day specified in the acceptance documents for transportation and in the calendar stamp of the station of departure. In case of incomplete day, full day is accepted in the calculation of delivery times.

Terms of delivery are the time of sending and receiving operations, the time of arrival of goods and the time of additional operations specified in the road trip, as well as the Charter (for example, the suspension of cargo by customs and other government agencies, force majeure, military action, blockade, epidemic, etc.) includes the time allowed to extend the delivery time in the presence of circumstances [2-4].

Delivery shall be deemed to have taken place if the goods have been unloaded by rail before the expiration of the term of delivery specified at the designated railway station, or if the wagon (container) has been unloaded by means of the consignee. The date on which the railway notifies the consignee and the customs authorities (cargo under customs control) of the arrival of the goods at the destination station shall be recognized as the actual date of arrival of the goods at the destination station. In this case, the railway is not responsible for the suspension of cargo at the designated station, which is associated with customs clearance.

Delivery of wagons (containers) for unloading due to employment of the unloading front or other reasons related to the consignee shall be deemed delivered

during the shipment if the cargo arrived at the designated railway station before the expiration of the specified delivery period (Figure GU-23).

An empty wagon owned or leased by an organization or individual shall be deemed to have been delivered on time if it has reached the end of the delivery period at the designated station and the recipient or the owner of the railway station can be notified by the railway.

The railway shall be liable for delays in the delivery of cargo and empty wagons owned or leased by organizations and individuals. Pursuant to Article 128 of the Charter, if the railway fails to prove its guilt in delaying the delivery of goods, the railway shall pay a penalty of 6% of the fare to the consignee for each day of delay, assuming the incomplete day in full. , but not more than 30% of the rent. A fine of the same amount shall be levied on the railway for delay in delivery of an empty wagon owned or leased by an organization or individual.

In order to comply with the terms of delivery of goods: to ship the received cargo usually on the day of receipt and at least the next day; to comprehensively reduce the number of car stops at technical and freight stations; to increase the speed of trains; In mixed transport, special attention should be paid to improving the interaction of railway transport with other types of transport and the implementation of other technological operations in a timely manner [5].

Loading and unloading times are the time spent loading and unloading goods in a mechanized or non-mechanized manner, taking into account the time spent on preparation, auxiliary and finishing operations. Terms of loading and unloading of various goods by mechanized or non-mechanized methods are given in Annexes 1, 2, 3 and 4 of Section 13 of the Rules of Carriage of Goods.

The start of loading (unloading) on the station tracks is the time when the wagons are loaded (unloaded), and the end of the loading (unloading) is the readiness of the station to load all the wagons in the consignment at the same time from the consignor (consignee) is the time you receive the message. For a group of wagons of different periods placed on the loading (unloading) on the front, the time specified for the wagon with the largest period of loading (unloading) is given.

Results. The time limits specified in Annexes 1, 2, 3 and 4 of Section 13 of the Rules of Carriage of Goods shall be used to regulate the time of stopping and unloading of wagons at the places of use by consignors and consignees, as well as the operation of railways or the import and export of wagons. is used to determine the rate of loading and unloading of wagons when concluding and re-contracting.

If the company uses loading and unloading machines not provided for in Annexes 3 and 4 of Section 13 of the Rules of Carriage of Goods, or carries out loading and unloading by mechanized methods, the company develops and submits for loading and unloading terms for approval by the regional railway department . The development of such deadlines is carried out in accordance with the "Guidelines for the calculation of mechanized loading and unloading times on wagons" in Annex 5 to Section 13 of the Rules of Carriage of Goods in the following order.

When determining the loading and unloading times of wagons, it is necessary to take into account the maximum joint performance of individual work operations. The estimated timing of loading or unloading on wagons is as follows:

a) preparation operations ($t_{\text{рай}}$) - removal of seals and wire ties, opening of doors and openings, installation or removal of barriers in the doorway, installation of columns, beams and bridges, test sampling, etc .;

b) finishing operations ($t_{\text{тыр}}$) - closing of car doors and openings, installation of seals and wire ties, fastening of cargoes, cleaning of wagons after unloading, leveling of overloaded, etc .;

c) the sum of the times of loading or unloading of the wagon on the mechanisms, taking into account the time of rolling of the mechanisms or wagons.

When loading or unloading group wagons, preparation operations with all wagons, finishing operations with the exception of the first and all wagons, loading or unloading operations with other wagons except the last shall be performed and therefore not taken into account in calculating the total loading or unloading time. The loading or unloading time of n wagons is determined using the following formula:

$$T = t_{\text{рай}} + (n / m) \cdot t_{\text{юк}} + t_{\text{тыр}} ,$$

where m is the number of wagons that can be loaded or unloaded at the same time when using multiple mechanisms.

The time taken to load the load from the wagon or to unload the load from the wagon is determined by the following formula:

$$t_{\text{юк}} = (q_{\text{B}} \cdot 60) / Q_{\text{T}} + t_{\text{эп}}$$

where q_{B} is the average mass of the load in the wagon, t ;

Q_{T} - technical efficiency of the loading and unloading mechanism, t / h ;

$t_{\text{эп}}$ - to auxiliary operations in the process of loading and unloading time spent, min.

Operations that are performed on the handle, such as preparation, finishing and ancillary operations, as well as hooking and unloading of loads, and therefore cannot be determined by calculations, are determined on the basis of timing observations.

Discussion. All charges that must be levied by the railway for the carriage of goods on domestic routes must be paid by the shipper at the station of departure, until the goods are accepted for carriage and the goods are delivered in accordance with the procedure established by the railway.

When transporting goods on domestic routes crossing the transit sections of the railways of foreign countries involved in the carriage of goods, the fees for the territory of the transit sections shall be paid by the forwarding organization that has a contract with the transit railway.

Payments for the carriage of imported goods across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be made by the freight forwarding organization having a contract for the provision of freight forwarding services for the carriage of goods across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the terms of the contract of delivery between the consignee and the railway, is increased.

Export is carried out by the consignor at the station of departure or by a forwarding organization that has a contract for the provision of freight forwarding services for the carriage of goods across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the terms of the settlement agreement for the carriage of goods across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Payments for the carriage of transit cargo across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be made by freight forwarding organizations that have a contract for the provision of freight forwarding services across the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Payments added at the time of acceptance of goods for carriage shall be indicated by numbers and inscriptions in the appropriate columns of the set of transport documents.

The station, in the manner prescribed by the railway, draws up the relevant documents for the calculation of the charges to be paid for the specified railway services and submits them to the shippers (consignees) for payment.

All calculations for the carriage of goods are made at the station of destination until the delivery of goods to the consignee is formalized. The toll charged is determined correctly, including the low costs incurred, as well as the charges incurred along the way and at the designated station.

In case of indebtedness for railway services (transportation, additional work and services), the consignor or consignee shall be fined in the manner prescribed by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The railway has the right to keep the cargo until the previous transportation payments are made and the existing debt for previous transportation services is paid off. Penalties are imposed for keeping wagons and containers empty during their detention.

Payment in cash for railway services requires compliance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

All expenses related to rail transportation, not provided for in the applicable tariffs and incurred for reasons not related to the railway, must be reimbursed.

When registering a consignment note on international flights, records of payment of freight for transit sections of the railways of the countries participating in the carriage shall be attached to the relevant column with information on the consignor's payment for transit railways.

Taking into account the idleness of wagons and the norms of idleness, liability for non-compliance with the terms of wagon rotation

During loading and unloading of wagons during the service of the station track by the railway locomotive, the time of loading and unloading of wagons is calculated from the moment of actual placement of wagons in loading or unloading places until the station receives written notice from the owner of freight.

During the maintenance of the station tracks by the locomotive of their owners, the time of stagnation of wagons on the railway station tracks is calculated from the time of placing the wagons on the tracks in preparation for departure.

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